

Designing a Public Bench by PrEmo

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Abstract: The aim of this study is designing a new generation of public benches in the playgrounds. At this moment, the available public benches in playgrounds in Iran are not suitable enough to satisfy children's and parents' physical and emotional needs. For this study QFD and Kansei Engineering method was used. These methods are the useful methodologies that help the designers to provide users' emotional needs. The main target of a city is to make a creative and satisfying environment for people who live in. Fifty parents, twenty five women and twenty five men were selected randomly among the bench users in a playground. They were asked to describe their feelings about their favorite bench. Regarding users' expressions, two different concepts were generated by two methods. In order to evaluate the users' feelings regarding the two final concepts, another study was carried out with 25 participators. The PrEMO model was used and it was concluded that the QFD concept could have more positive affects on users.

Keywords: *Affect, Emotions, Public Bench, Kansei Engineering, QFD.*

1. Introduction

When a designer starts to design a new product, it would be needed to integrate the prospective users' demands and wishes. While there are various users' needs, the functional and emotional needs have been recognized as primary importance for users' satisfaction. So not only technical and objective needs are important, but also aesthetic, emotional, and other experiential factors must be considered. The development of modern technologies made many similar products functionally comparable. So, users may find it difficult to distinguish and choose one product to buy and use. In this regard, it is necessary to design products by engaging users' emotions and feelings [1].

The terms emotion and feeling are currently used rather indiscriminately. Emotions are specific and consistent physical states. These states are specified as collections of physiological responses made by particular brain systems when the organism represents certain objects or situations. Feelings in turn, are the private and mental experience of emotions. Affect is used as generic term for both emotion and feeling [2].

Affect or affective states covers emotions and feelings and it is a user's psychological responses to the design details of a product [3]. The term "affect" is used to describe an internal feeling. It is an Explicit or implicit "liking" for some object, person, or position is viewed as an evaluative judgment. When we use the term "affect" to describe stimuli, it is in relation to evoked feeling states [4]. Affect can have a

significant influence on choice processes and it is the basis for the formation of human values and judgments [5].

A city is a large masterpiece that has creators as many as its citizens. The main target of a city is to make a creative and satisfying environment for people who live in. Quality of the public services is considered as a critical factor for the national economic performance and the living standards. The main challenge for public sectors is to offer a better service to the citizens [6].

Benches are one of the common public furniture types. They have an important role to bring people relief and sense of peacefulness. Fun and comfortable benches in parks and playgrounds could make adults and children happier and more satisfied. Therefore, there is a vital need to know people values and serve them what they want. Often it could be possible to understand the people satisfactions by measuring their affective responses. However the users' affective responses to particular products are not easy to articulate. To overcome this problem, researchers have proposed the use of a variety of tools which basically facilitate the expression of affective emotional issues [7].

In order to find out the Iranian people desires and design a new generation of public playground benches, two studies were carried out.

2. First Study

The purpose of the first study was to design a new type of playground benches. To design a new generation of public seats, two different methods were used. Quality Function Deployment and Kansei engineering were used to generate concepts. The best concepts of each method were selected and developed.

To perform this study, at first the Iranian people needs in Kish Island for public seats were identified. Kish Island which located in south of Iran, has a tropical climate with very hot and humid weather. The available public benches in playgrounds in Kish are made from concrete and do not have any relation with playgrounds environment (Figure 1). The parents who used to come to playgrounds with their children were selected as the target group. Fifty people, 25 women and 25 men from target group were selected randomly in a playground. They were interviewed and asked to explain their need and their feelings about their favorite public seats in the playground.

Figure 1. An available public bench in playground in Kish Island

Based on users' interests two new benches were designed by two different methods.

2.1. Applying QFD to design a new public bench in playground

Quality Function Deployment establishes user value using the voice of customer and transforms that value to design, production, and manufacturing process characteristics [8]. QFD method works with a matrix for mapping the voice of customer to the voice of engineer. In order to perform QFD process in House of Quality matrix, the users' wants about their favorite bench were translated to the clear design instructions. In the next step, these Voices of Customers were rated by them from 1 to 100 percent of importance. As Table 1 shows having curved corners, Having Back, being short and comfortable the most important attributes of the new bench while having low price and swinging have the less importance.

Table 1. The Rated Voice of Customers

Voice of Customer	Importance Rating
Comfortable	90%
Curved corners	100%
Short	90%
Exciting	80%
Having Back	90%
Thermal Acoustic	70%
Active	60%
Usable in all directions	60%
Having Shade	30%
Having Table	50%
Swinging	20%
Low Price	20%
Vandal Proof	70%

Following these steps, a market research carried out in order to identify the best public benches as competitors. Then the technical specifications of these playgrounds obtained from their catalogues and manuals and applied in QFD process. These technical specifications were classified to several items, including; Material of seat, Material of leg, Material of back, Area of seat, Height of seat, Color type, Form, Color variation, Texture, Joints and Thermal resistance. They were entered as measurable parameters in House of Quality matrix that could be used for design (Figure 2).

Figure 2. The QFD matrix

	Seat material	Leg material	Back material	Seat Area	Seat Height	Color type	Forms	Thermal resistance	Color Variety	Hardness	Texture	Joints
EC importance	29	25	35	10	11	19	57	10	13	18	21	24
targets	Poly ethylene	Poly ethylene	Poly ethylene	45 X 45 cm	40 cm	self Color Material	Cubic forms	Poly ethylene	3 colors, Red, Blue, Yellow	Attachable on the base	Soft	Non joint

Figure 3. The Target Results of the QFD matrix

At the next step, the relationship between voice of customers and technical specifications were identified. A weight of 1-3-5 was used in this study for presenting the relationships. Filled point was used for showing a strong relationship between a customer attribute and an engineering characteristic. While an empty point was used for presenting medium relationship and a triangle for weak relationship.

To find critical product requirements, sum of each column in center part of the House of Quality matrix was calculated. The results as the Engineering Characteristics Importance were shown in the House of Quality matrix in Figure 2. As Figure 2 shows, the form bench with 57 scores is the most important technical specification. The material of the bench in back, seat and legs and their joints are the next

important technical issues with 35, 29,25 and 24 scores. While the thermal resistance and sitting area has less scores.

After obtaining the critical engineering characteristics, the target value for each technical detail was investigated from the competitors' specifications and standards. Each target value was chosen from the best engineering characteristic. These are the values which used as targets in finding sub-solutions and generating alternatives phase in design process. The result of target value is presented in Figure 3.

Regarding the target values which obtained from QFD matrix, several concepts were generated. Due to the users' interests and voice of customers, one of these concepts was selected as the final concept.

The final concept consists of two parts with cubic forms. These two parts are the back and seat of the bench.

The height of the seat is 40 centimeter and its sitting area is 45x45 centimeter.

The material of the bench is Polyethylene in red, blue and yellow colors. Different textures could be applied on the face of the seat. The back and seat of each bench would be located in different situations.

This bench is usable for all directions and users are able to put their bag and stuff on the surface of the back. The final concept of the bench is shown in Figure4.

Figure 4. The final concept that designed with QFD

2.2. Applying Kansei Engineering to obtain design parameters of playground

Kansei Engineering shows how Kansei is translated into design of a product. It is a design method which captures the user's considerations and feelings and translates these emotional aspects into concrete design. The most common way of measuring the Kansei is through the words [9].

The first step is to assess the users' perception about their favorite bench. Therefore their feelings and desires have to be identified and expressed with Kansei words. In order to apply Kansei Engineering method, the words which obtained from interview were considered as Kansei words. One hundred twenty five adjectives were obtained as Kansei words.

In second step, these Kansei words were analyzed and categorized to be able to measure the customer's perception. For structuring the Kansei words, from each category a word or a group of words were chosen as a representative. So the number of them reduced to 4 words as higher-level Kansei words. Table2 shows these chosen higher-level Kansei words.

In next step according to the product domain, bench properties and its details identified. Regarding the Kansei words, bench specifications and playground design specifications, many concepts were generated. Due to the users' interests and desires, one of these concepts was selected as the best and final concept.

Table 2. The Chosen Higher Level Kansei Words

Higher Level Kansei Words
Comfortable
Safe
Attractive
Soft
Short

The final concept is a bench which made of soft LDPE (Low Density Poly Ethylene). It has flexible seat heights for different users from children to elderly people. Its height is considered from 40 centimeter height to 17 centimeter. The overall dimension of the bench is 120 centimeter length and 45 centimeter width for sitting. The form of the bench is organic and curved. The colors of the bench are in red, yellow, orange, blue and violet. Users are able to sit on it from two directions at the same time. The angle of the back is considered from 95 degree to 120 degree for the most comfortable position. This concept is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. The final concept that designed with Kansei Engineering Method

The final concept formed due to children's Kansei words. Therefore, the means of each Kansei word can be seen in the concept. The relation between different parts of the concept and Kansei words is presented in table 3. As table 3 shows each bench specification was designed due to the related kansei word. For example flexible height from 17 centimeter to 40 centimeter height was designed in bench for short and comfortable use.

Table 3. The Relationship between Higher Level Kansei words and bench specifications

Higher-Level Kansei Words	Bench Specifications
Comfortable	Curved and organic forms, 95 to 120 degree angle between back and seat, useable in 2 directions
Safe	Curved corners
Attractive	Colorful appearance in red, yellow, orange, blue and violet
Soft	LDPE
Short	Flexible height from 17 to 40 cm height

3. Second Study

The aim of the second study was to evaluate the two new concepts of public bench regarding users' emotional responses.

1.3. Methods

In order to evaluate these two concepts, the Product Emotion Measurement Instrument (PrEmo) was used. PrEmo is a non-verbal self-report instrument that measures 14 emotions that are often elicited by product design. Of these 14 emotions, seven are pleasant, and seven are unpleasant.

Instead of relying on the use of words, respondents can report their emotions with the use of expressive cartoon animations. In the instrument, each of the 14 measured emotions is portrayed by an animation by means of dynamic facial, bodily, and vocal expressions. Figure 1 shows some examples of the cartoons, and Figure 2 shows the measurement interface [10]. These emotions are shown in figure 6.

<i>Pleasant emotions</i>	<i>Unpleasant emotions</i>
Desire	Indignation
Pleasant surprise	Contempt
Inspiration	Disgust
Amusement	Unpleasant surprise
Admiration	Dissatisfaction
Satisfaction	Disappointment
Fascination	Boredom

Figure 6. The PrEmo Emotions Model

Twenty five people from parents who brought children to a playground in Kish Island participated in the study. A showroom was prepared and the two concepts were presented in same condition on A3 papers. The participators were asked to select one emotional character from cartoon board as their feelings about each concept. The emotional characters in cartoon board are shown in Figure 7. All these answers were collected and analyzed for each concept.

Figure 7. The PrEmo Emotional characters

2.3. Results

The results of the PrEmo study about the concept that designed by QFD method are shown in Table 4. As Table 4 shows from the 25 participants, 22 people had pleasant emotion about the QFD bench. Seven people of participants had pleasant surprise feeling and five of them were satisfied. Four people found the Bench amusing. Also three of participants thought that it was a desirable bench while the other three people had inspiration feeling. There is only one answer as dissatisfaction and two of the participants had no sense about it. As Figure 8 shows 88% of participants' feeling are Pleasant Feeling and 4% of them are classified as Negative Feeling. Eight percent of these feelings are No sense.

Table 4. The Results of PrEmo Study for QFD concept

Pleasant Emotion	Person	Unpleasant Emotion	Person
Desire	3	Indignation	
Pleasant Surprise	7	Contempt	
Inspiration	3	Disgust	
Amusement	4	Unpleasant Surprise	
Admiration		Dissatisfaction	1
Satisfaction	5	Disappointment	
Fascination		Boredom	
No Sense			2

Figure 8. The Results of PrEmo study for QFD concept

The results of the PrEmo study about the concept that designed by Kansei Engineering method are shown in Table 5. As Table 5 shows from the 25 participants, 21 people had positive emotion about the Kansei bench.

Six participants admired this concept and five of them found it amusing. Also four people in this study had inspiration feeling while the other four participants were satisfied with it. Two people among 25 participants were fascinated by this bench.

There is only one answer as unpleasant surprise feeling and three of the participants had no sense about it. As Figure 9 shows 84% of participants' feeling are Pleasant Feeling and 4% of them are classified as Negative Feeling. Twelve percent of these feelings are No sense.

Table 5. The Results of PrEmo Study for Kansei Engineering concept

Pleasant Emotion	Person	Unpleasant Emotion	Person
Desire		Indignation	
Pleasant Surprise		Contempt	
Inspiration	4	Disgust	
Amusement	5	Unpleasant Surprise	1
Admiration	6	Dissatisfaction	
Satisfaction	4	Disappointment	
Fascination	2	Boredom	
No Sense			3

Figure 9. The Results of PrEmo study for Kansei Engineering concept

3.3. Discussion

According to the first study, the collections of users' words indicate that they want comfortable, soft, short and attractive benches in playgrounds. Benches have some harmony with the playground environment. They need a comfortable seat for rest and watch their children playing. In QFD matrix these attributes were translated to the technical specification of a new bench. A new bench that has curved forms, soft and smooth textures with different colors. By employing the QFD results, several concepts were generated and the best of them were selected as the final concept.

Final concept was a cubic bench with separated seat and back in three different colors which made from thermal acoustic and soft polyethylene material. It had curved corners and places to put their bags and stuffs. The surface of the seat could be used for performing funny and educational textures for playgrounds. The cubic forms of the bench were suitable for using in all directions at the same time.

The kansei words show that users liked comfortable, safe, soft, attractive and short bench. The concept which designed by Kansei Engineering is a bench with flexible seat height for different users. It is made of soft LDPE material in various colors.

As Results showed, participators had more positive feelings about the concept that designed with QFD method.

The most people (28%) in the study found this concept pleasantly surprising which was stronger than the positive emotions which people mentioned about the Kansei bench concept. This feeling was related to its simple form and color which could be arranged in different shapes. While the most people (24%) in the

study on Kansei bench believed that it is mostly admirable for its organic and unusual shape which was weaker emotion rather than pleasant surprise feeling.

For both concepts only one people had negative feeling. About the QFD bench concept, one people had dissatisfaction feeling with it. While one people unpleasantly surprised about the Kansei concept which is more serious negative emotion than dissatisfaction. Four people in this study did not fell any sense regarding benches from the emotional board.

4.3. Conclusion

In this study QFD and Kansei Engineering method were used to capture the Iranian users' desires to design a new bench in the playgrounds in Kish Island. Then the selected concepts from each method were evaluated by PrEmo to identify the users' feelings about it. The results of the study show that participants loved the new bench which designed by QFD method. It seems this concept had more positive feelings and affects on them because of simple and cubic form. Employing different colors, textures and arrangements, curved lines and soft material makes users surprised.

This study also showed that QFD with the ability of translating users' needs and desire to Engineering characteristics could be a very useful applied methodology. It captured the people's feelings and desires to design a bench, which pleasingly surprised them to sit and experience happy and calm moments.

4. References

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